

'Gene order' analysis reveals the history of *The Canterbury Tales* manuscripts

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Chaucer's *Canterbury Tales* is a series of loosely-connected stories told by fictional pilgrims. Extant manuscripts of *The Canterbury Tales*, copied by hand in the fifteenth century, show many different orderings of the tales and linking passages¹. These differences are largely due to rearrangements of items (tales and links) by scribes, who found it difficult to establish an appropriate order even in the earliest manuscripts (references ^{1,2} and pp. 307-343 in reference ³). The order of items may reveal genealogical relationships among manuscripts, but previous scholars have tried to discern these relationships without quantitative analysis^{1,3-8}. However, the transmission of item order from ancestral to descendant manuscripts, with occasional modifications, is analogous to the transmission of the order of genes on a genome⁹, and can be analysed in a similar way. Here, we use methods developed for the analysis of gene order to produce a phylogenetic tree based on the order of tales and links in *The Canterbury Tales*. Our results suggest that there was no clearly established order for the *Tales* when the earliest manuscripts were written.

We calculated the breakpoint distance (a measure of the number of rearrangements of items) between the order of items in each pair of manuscripts and early printed editions, and estimated a phylogenetic tree for these distances (see Methods). Our approach is identical to analyses of gene order^{9,10}, except that we have to deal with missing data caused by physical damage. The resulting tree (Fig.1) recovers many groups of manuscripts suggested by manual studies of tale order¹. The manuscript codes in the tree are coloured according to these groups, and there is a separate common ancestor for most manuscripts of each colour. The exception is that the B (blue) and D (purple) groups are not clearly separated on our tree. However, the order of items in all B and D manuscripts may have been derived from a single exemplar used for commercial copying⁴. Furthermore, our tree based on item order shows some agreements with a tree based on word variation within the texts. The relationships among manuscripts based on word variation shift considerably between sections of text, because different sections of a manuscript may have been copied from different exemplars¹¹ or may represent different stages of authorial revision (pp. 74-79 in reference 12). However, for a subset of 21 manuscripts having relatively constant relationships over a short section of the text (the General Prologue: see *Analysis Workshop* in reference 13), trees based on word variation (Fig. 2a) and the order of tales and linking passages (Fig. 2b) are more similar than would be expected by chance (Fig. 2c: Wilcoxon two-sample test, $t_s = 40.1$, $P < 0.001$).

The item order tree (Fig.1) allows us to refine the conclusions of previous scholars. Manuscripts that were previously classified as 'anomalous' (coloured black in Fig. 1)¹, can be separated into several different types. Many (Ch, Cx2, Ha4, Hg, Ld1, To) fall in an intermediate position between the more clearly defined groups, which would make them difficult to classify, although they show some similarities in the order of items. For example, Ch, Ld1 and To appear to descend from a common ancestor, and Cx2 and Ha4 are also separated by only a few nodes. Analysis of the text of all these

manuscripts suggests that they represent at least two independent lines of descent from the ancestor of the whole tradition, and that they are close to this ancestor^{11,14}. Two others (Ps, Se) are related to the A group of manuscripts, coloured red in Fig. 1. The last two 'anomalous' manuscripts (Nl, Hk) have quite different orders from any other extant manuscripts. Both appear to have been copied from collections of fragments, and both show shifts in textual affiliation between sections (reference 11 and pages 49, 77 in reference 8).

The tree in Fig. 1 is unrooted, so we cannot immediately determine which extant order is closest to the ancestor of the tradition. Even the earliest manuscripts (e.g. Hengwrt (Hg), Ellesmere (El), Cambridge Dd.4.24 (Dd), Corpus Christi Oxford 198 (Cp) and Harley 7334 (Ha4)), which we might expect to be close to the ancestor, are widely separated on the tree. If Chaucer had a definite arrangement for the items, accurately represented in an extant manuscript, it would be hard to explain why the extant manuscripts have many different orders. Other literary works such as Boccaccio's *Decameron* and Gower's *Confessio Amantis*, produced around the same time as *The Canterbury Tales* (or a little earlier, in the case of the *Decameron*) and sharing a similar form, show little variation in the order of sections among extant manuscripts^{5,15}. This is consistent with Chaucer's original copy of *The Canterbury Tales* being unfinished and disordered (reference 7 and pages 165-178 in reference 6), and some sections may have circulated independently during Chaucer's lifetime (reference 1, page 4 in reference 8, page 285 in reference 3).

Elsewhere, we showed how small-scale patterns of word variation between manuscripts within a section of *The Canterbury Tales* can be successfully analysed using phylogenetic methods^{11,14}. Here, we establish a further parallel between the order of genes on a genome and the order of items in a text. Constructing a phylogenetic tree based on the order of items has allowed us to hypothesise relationships among

previously unclassified manuscripts, which can now be tested using data on word variation. Phylogenetic methods provide an objective visualisation of the complex relationships among a set of genealogically-related items. These rigorous methods, combined with the increasing availability of manuscript data in electronic form, will change the way scholars approach literary traditions.

Methods

Item order data

We transcribed the order of tales in all reasonably complete extant manuscripts and early printed editions of *The Canterbury Tales* from Charts I-IV in reference 1. We recoded these data to include linking passages as well as tales. We treated homologous links (used, with slight alterations in their text, to connect different pairs of tales in different manuscripts) as the same items (treating them as distinct items gave similar results). We deleted one manuscript (Glasgow Hunterian 197) in which several items occur twice, because our distance measure does not deal with such cases. This left 56 manuscripts with 11 to 50 items each (median 43). The Hengwrt manuscript (Hg in Fig. 1) was rebound in a slightly different order after production. We used the reconstructed original order¹ (using the rebound order gave similar results).

Distance measure for item order

We calculated pairwise distances between manuscripts based on differences in item order. The natural choice for a distance measure is edit distance, the minimum number of editing operations (here insertions/deletions, adding/removing one or more items; and transpositions, moving one or more items to a new location) needed to convert one order into another. However, calculating edit distances is difficult¹⁶, and the loss of

sections due to physical damage in many manuscripts made it impossible to calculate the number of insertions/deletions. We therefore used scaled breakpoint distance between the items common to each pair of manuscripts, which is approximately linearly related to the actual number of transpositions when few transpositions have occurred¹⁰, as in most of our data. Breakpoint distance is the number of items common to both manuscripts and having different right-hand neighbours. For example, between hypothetical manuscripts i and j

$$\begin{aligned} i &= s \ 1 \ 2 \ 3 \ 4 \ e \\ j &= s \ 1|3|2|4 \ e \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

there are three breakpoints, indicated by $|$, out of five possible breakpoint sites. The dummy items s and e at the start and end of each manuscript ensure that a transposition of the first or last real item can create the same number of breakpoints as a transposition of any other item. To calculate breakpoint distance between a pair of manuscripts i and j in the presence of missing data, we first excluded all possible breakpoint sites at which either the left-hand or the right-hand item was missing. Let m_{ij} be the number of possible breakpoint sites remaining (resolved breakpoint sites), and let b_{ij} be the number of breakpoints among these resolved breakpoint sites. We scaled b_{ij} by the expected value for a pair of random manuscripts having the same number of resolved breakpoint sites, missing sections and items in common as the real manuscripts⁹. Let N_{ij} be the number of items (excluding s and e) common to i and j in their current state, and let $N'_{ij} \geq N_{ij}$ be the number of common items originally in both i and j , before any damage occurred. The probability that the right-hand neighbour of common item k is common item $k+1$ in both of a pair of random manuscripts is $1/N'_{ij}$, so we expect m_{ij}/N'_{ij} common items having the same right-hand neighbour in both manuscripts. The expected number of breakpoints between two random manuscripts having m_{ij} resolved breakpoint sites is

$$m_{ij} \left(1 - \frac{1}{N_{ij}} \right) \leq m_{ij} \left(1 - \frac{1}{N'_{ij}} \right) \leq m_{ij} \quad (2)$$

The lower limit occurs when no common items were lost, and the upper limit is approached if there are many lost common items. Thus in the presence of missing data, the limits on scaled breakpoint distance B_{ij} are

$$\frac{b_{ij}}{m_{ij}} \leq B_{ij} \leq \frac{b_{ij}}{m_{ij} \left(1 - \frac{1}{N_{ij}} \right)} \quad (3)$$

We present analyses of the upper limit on scaled breakpoint distance (range 0 to 0.65, median 0.18 excluding self distances), as we expect few lost common items. The lower limit on scaled breakpoint distance gave similar results.

Data on word variation in the General Prologue

Word variation data for Fig. 2a are from an electronic database¹³. We constructed the tree from mean character distances (number of observed word variants between manuscripts, scaled to the number of non-missing variant sites). All mean character distances were <0.23 so we did not correct for multiple hits.

Tree estimation

We used the PAUP*¹⁷ minimum-evolution heuristic search (tree bisection-reconnection, initial neighbour-joining tree), constrained to non-negative edge lengths. Manuscripts may have been copied more than once, so we do not require bifurcating trees. We therefore set edge lengths less than 10^{-8} to zero. We present trees with the shortest sums of edge lengths. Trees that were almost as short had similar topologies.

Tree comparison

We show agreements between trees in Fig.2 using Adams-2 consensus^{18,19} (disagreements appear as >3 edges from a point). We calculated partition distances²⁰ between the tree in Fig. 2a and 50000 Markovian random bifurcating trees (generating suitable non-bifurcating random trees is difficult). We compared these distances with those between the tree in Fig. 2a and a sample of 50000 bifurcating trees corresponding to the non-bifurcating trees in Fig. 2b, using a Wilcoxon two-sample test corrected for ties (page 430 in reference 21).

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Figure 1. Unrooted minimum evolution phylogenetic tree for the extant manuscripts of *The Canterbury Tales* based on the order of tales and linking

passages. Manuscripts are represented by the codes given on pp. 180-181 in reference 22, and are coloured according to the groups in reference 1: 'A' red; 'B' blue; 'anomalous' black; 'C' gold; 'D' purple. Edge lengths are to scale, in units of scaled breakpoint distance. Manuscripts grouped in lists are located in visually indistinguishable positions on the tree.

Figure 2. Comparisons between phylogenetic trees for *The Canterbury Tales* based on word variation and tale order. (a). Minimum evolution tree based on word variation in lines 1-500 of the General Prologue, for 21 manuscripts with constant relationships. Edge lengths are to scale, in units of mean character distance. (b). Adams-2 consensus of 532 minimum evolution trees based on the order of tales and linking passages, in the same 21 manuscripts. Edge lengths not to scale. (c). Adams-2 consensus between the trees in (a) and (b). Edge lengths not to scale. Manuscript codes and colours as in Fig. 1.